

School of Agroforestry

Introduction

The NEWTON project promotes traditional agroforestry knowledge and innovative solutions for the implementation of sustainable agroforestry systems with a participatory approach.

From 3 to 7 October 2022, at Tenuta di Paganico was held the agroforestry school. It was organized in five training module-days based on classroom lessons and field visits. The topics covered during the days were: agroforestry and forestry systems; forestry management and grazing; soil; certification and marketing.

The school involved 38 stakeholders, and it saw in particular the participation of many young farmers who are environmentally aware and interested in agroforestry as a strategy for more sustainable farm management.

Lessons learned

The school was a great success, particularly because many interested stakeholders were involved.

The critical point that emerged was the lack of economic data to support the (possible) adoption of agroforestry. From the meetings with the main actors involved it emerged that agroforestry is a promising system to contrast the abandonment of agricultural land and therefore maintain farmers' presence in the

internal and/or marginal areas while generating income. A further result was the raised awareness

by the actors involved of the importance of social and economic sustainability. That is a fundamental aspect for the application of more sustainable cropping systems in the next years, in order to mitigate climate change and make agroecosystems more resilient to changing conditions.

For further information contact

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The information presented in this factsheet was developed by the FOREST4EU partner, drawing on the innovations and knowledge generated by the indicated operational group with their explicit authorization.

Further information

<https://gonewton.it/>

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